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Open Science Policy of the Swiss Academy of Humanities and Social Sciences

0. Basics

- Four Golden Principles for Enhancing the Quality, Access and Impact of Research Infrastructures. Note from the League of European Research Universities LERU, November 2017 (<https://www.leru.org/publications/four-golden-principles-for-enhancing-the-quality-access-and-impact-of-research-infrastructures>)
- EOSC Declaration: European Open Science Cloud. New Research and Innovation Opportunities, Brussels 2017 (https://ec.europa.eu/research/openscience/pdf/eosc_declaration.pdf#view=fit&pagemode=none)
- The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship (Wilkinson et al., 2016, Scientific Data 3:160018), <https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18>
- COMMISSION RECOMMENDATION of 25.4.2018 on access to and preservation of scientific information (Brussels, 25.4.2018, C (2018) 2375 final) (http://ec.europa.eu/news-room/dae/document.cfm?doc_id=51636)
- Open Research Data Policy des SNF (http://www.snf.ch/de/derSnf/forschung-spolitische_positionen/open_research_data/Seiten/default.aspx)

1. Introduction

1.1 Motive and Aim

An Open Science Policy is part of a high-quality scientific practice. It guarantees access to research results (data and publications) of organisations and facilitates their re-use. Thus, the aim is achieved to provide available information as freely as possible and with few restrictions to a wide public. Moreover, the principles of access, presentation, data protection and re-use of research results are described. With this policy, the Swiss Academy of Humanities and Social Sciences (SAHS) intends to provide a basis for the implementation of «Open Science» within the research infrastructures¹ it supports.

¹ Research infrastructures are long-term planned mechanisms, resources and services which can be used by academic associations (and by others) and which provide lasting basics for high-quality and innovative research projects; see also *definitions* by the European Commission: <http://ec.europa.eu/research/infrastructures/index.cfm?pg=about> und European Commission: Legal framework for a European Research Infrastructure Consortium – ERIC, Practical Guidelines, p. 11, DOI: [10.2777/79873](https://doi.org/10.2777/79873).

1.2 Scope and Field of Application

The Open Science Policy is used on research infrastructures (RI) which are significantly supported by the SAHS. At present these are: Data and Service Center for the Humanities DaSCH, Swiss Diplomatic Documents Dodis, Historical Dictionary of Switzerland HDS, infoclio.ch, Swiss Inventory of Coin Finds SICF, «Année Politique Suisse» APS, «Nationale Wörterbücher» NWB and editions which were transferred from the Swiss National Science Foundation (NSF) to the Swiss Academy of Humanities and Social Sciences (SAHS). The SAHS can also use these policy principles on other RIs if they are significantly supported by it.

The aspects named under item two are to be understood as guidelines which have to be referred to by implementing Open Science for the above-mentioned projects. Possible reasons for excluding projects from the guidelines are: if an implementation is impossible, the context is not of relevance, the complexity of effort and costs is unduly high.

2. Policy Areas

2.1 FAIR Guiding Principles

- The «FAIR Guiding Principles»² apply to all items mentioned below. In line with the implementation of the Open Science Policy, the RI of the SAHS check all domains with regard to the compatibility with FAIR Principles and take, if necessary, further measures.

2.2 Measures for Quality Assurance

- The RI define processes for the quality assurance of contents published by them and present these either as a quality manual or as Wikis. If possible, these processes should be put on the RI websites.

2.3 Data Standards

- For definable databases, machine-readable metadata are recorded which comply with the Dublin Core-Scheme or another known standard.
- If possible, the data should comply with a standardised metadata-scheme (XML, TEI, IIIF etc.)
- Providing that existent and practicable, standardised vocabularies/classifications are used as information in some of the data fields.

2.4 Long-term Availability of Data

- The RI develop and implement processes for securing long-term availability of the provided data and programme structures. Where possible, international standards should be followed and external providers of such services (e.g. Switch or DLCM) should be involved.
- As far as necessary, the RI maintain documentation and inventories of the applied hardware and infrastructure to guarantee the service of the RI.

2.5 Software Code

- If possible, no proprietary systems are applied. In case of internal or external software development, efforts have to be made that the code is available on public domains for software development, so that a Community-Building can take place.

² The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship (Wilkinson et al., 2016, Scientific Data 3:160018), <https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18>.

2.6 Data Access

- It is the aim to provide free access to as much data as possible. Before free access to data can be made available, all legal aspects (copy right and data protection act) have to be resolved. In order to transparently regulate the access to data, Creative Commons Licences have to be indicated. The following principles have to be prevailed: Open accessible repositories will be made available to the public (CC0 Public Domain), if no legal restrictions exist. Data enhancement (database entries, comments, indexation etc.) are to be made accessible to the public under license CC BY or CC BY-SA. Licenses which differ from these, such as CC NC (non-commercial) and CC ND (no derivative) must be substantiated. The CC-licences are to be machine-readable.
- Publications (editions, monographs, articles, dossiers, reports etc.) from the RI are basically published as Gold Open Access and feature a digital identifier (e.g. DOI). Retention periods of generally 12 months can be applied for if well-founded circumstances exist. The publications are provided with machine-readable meta data.
- The software systems in use offer a gateway to the application programming which particularly allows access to data bases of the RI in order to guarantee data transfer and data exchange.

2.7 Use of Data

- All data are provided with a persistent identification, whereby these are made to definite reference data (DOI, Handle, ARK, URI etc.).
- The operators of the RI encourage re-use of data via the research and other fields. They publish their own articles using data of the RI and propose publications and research projects. According to their potential, the RI-persons responsible launch research projects and maintain the contact and exchange with academic institutions. In case of interest, they also offer their service for running courses. The RI generate annual statistics about their public relations and specify publications in which data of the RI have been used, provided that they are known to them.
- In collaboration with users, the RI follow the principles of the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) where necessary.

3. Implementation

- According to the SAHS-Multiannual Planning 2017–2020, the RI mentioned under 2.1 will have developed, implemented and appropriately released an Open Data Policy till 2020. In doing so, explicit reference to the FAIR-Principles has to be made (see 2.1). A statement has to be given if the FAIR-Principles are not followed.
- The effectiveness of the agreed measures will be checked regularly.
- Having completed the implementation of the Open Science Policy, the RI are to be listed on relevant repositories (re3data.org, OpenDOAR, FAIRsharing.org, disciplinary repositories etc.) and it should be checked whether a certification (e.g. CoreTrustSeal) of the RI is practicable.

Adopted by the Board of the SAHS on 22 February 2019.